

HUMAN RIGHTS IN INDIAN AND GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE

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Introduction

The history of human kind has been firmly associated with the struggle of individual against injustice, exploitation and disdain. The recognition, first at national and later at international level of human rights is one of the most remarkable manifestations of the struggle. Recognition, protection and implementation of human rights are a very important and complicated issue because there is no agreed definition and understanding of the term 'Human Right' It is a dynamic concept and it endeavours to adopt itself to the needs of the day. For this reason, the definition and understanding of term depends much on the condition and opinion prevailing in the given society at a given time and it attains new dimensions with the march of history. To put it simply human rights constitute those very rights which one has precisely because of being a human. Maurice Cranston defines human rights as "the rights which belong to man, only because he is a man."

In the words of Subhash C. Kashyap, "the fundamental norm governing the concept of human right is that of the respect for human personality and its absolute worth. Human rights may be said as those fundamental rights to which every man or Woman inhabiting in any part of the world should be deemed entitled merely by virtue of having being born a human being." J. Donnelly said, "Human rights are those held simply by virtue of being a Person. To have a human right one need not be or do anything special, other than to be born as human being." Though various authors have ventured and defined human rights, yet as it stands there is no precise and universally accepted definition of human rights, Edward Lawson's definition can be considered as the most comprehensive and appealing He, in the Encyclopaedia of Human Rights says, "human rights are the universally accepted principles and rules that support mortality and that makes possible for each member of the human family to realize his or her full potential and to live life in an atmosphere of freedom, justice and peace." Basic to the concept of human rights is the desire of the people to live the life of a man, and not the slave who lives on the whims of the rulers. In other words, it means the desires of the people to live a dignified life. The present paper focuses on the evolution and development of the concept of human rights in Indian as well as in the global context.

Three Generations of Human Rights

Human rights are the product of an evolutionary process. Different philosopher and circumstances have added new rights to the original list of human rights. The first generation rights includes civil and political rights, these rights were first developed in the liberal traditions and considered to be the original set of human rights. Second, the economic social and cultural rights

which have come to be known as the second generation human rights. Marx and his followers first highlighted these rights. Third, a group of new rights, which is called third generation human rights, started their claim to be included in the human rights only after the emergence of third world in the form of developing countries. These third generation rights emerged due to mainly two reasons; first the independence of the third world countries and second, the newly recognized threats to the entire mankind. Karl Vasak calls it the rights to solidarity and included four rights in this category. They are right to development, the right to a healthy and ecologically balanced environment, the right to peace, and the right to ownership of the common heritage of mankind.'

Now we are also talking about fourth and fifth generation of rights. The fourth generation corresponds to collective rights of identity groups such as LGBT. The fifth generation refers to the rights of humanity. Specially in relation to environment issue. But still, it is not very clear and controversy is there regarding the types of rights to be included in these fourth & fifth generation of rights."

Human Rights in Global Perspective: Evolution and Development

The concept of 'human rights' came some what late in the vocabulary of mankind. The term came in common use only after World War II. It was made current by the United Nations. 'Universal Declaration of Human Rights', in 1948. In other words, the concept of human rights is very old but the general recognition of its validity is new. Some scholars trace its origin back to the ancient period. According to some scholars the concept of human rights is as first reflected in ancient Greece and Roman thought. In the literature and philosophy both of Greece and Rome there are abundant statements acknowledging laws of the God and that of nature, and such laws were understood to take precedence over laws made by the state. In ancient history, as Bajwa argues, we also come across many moral principles in the name of 'Dharma' and 'Danda'.

The idea of natural law continues even after Roman period which forwarded the cause of human rights. However, natural law, at this stage was considered as will of God revealed to men by holy scriptures. In the form of natural law human rights are further promoted in the middle ages. St. Thomas Aquinas had tried to make a classic attempt to harmonise the teachings of the church with those of natural laws. The modern development of the human rights concept began during 17th and 18th century. The scientific and intellectual achievements of the 17th century, the discoveries of Galileo and Newton, the materialism of Hobbes, the rationalism of Rene Descartes and G. W. Leibniz, the pantheism of Spinoza, the empiricism of Francis Bacon and John Locke encouraged a belief in natural law and universal order. During the 18th century, the so called 'Age Of Enlightenment' a growing confidence in human reason and in the perfectibility of human affairs led to its more comprehensive expression in the writings of English Philosopher John Locke and the works of Montesquieu, Voltaire and Rousseau. John Locke, the Father of modern liberalism argued in detail. Mainly in "Two Treatises of Government" (1688). Those certain rights like right to life, liberty and property self evidently pertain to individuals as human beings because they even existed in the 'state of nature' before human kind entered into civil society. Rousseau raised the flamboyant slogan of 'liberty, equality and fraternity'. He wanted People to enjoy their liberty, equality and fraternity, within a political setup. His assertion that man "is everywhere in chains" is an assertion Rousseau wanted everyone to accept.⁸

After the decline of natural law conception of human rights, positive law evolved the legislation became the main source of human rights. The prominent writers in this regard are Austin and Bentham. Under positive law instead of human rights being absolute, they can be given, taken away and, modified by a society to suit its needs. Bentham sums up the essence of the positivist view as: "Right is a child of law; from real laws come real rights, but from imaginary law, from 'laws of nature' come imaginary rights..... Natural right is simple; nonsense."

This transfer of abstract ideas regarding human rights and their relation to the will of nature into concrete laws is exemplified best by various legal documents that specifically described these rights in detail.

Modern historians trace the origin of human rights to 'Magna Carta'. It was a charter of concessions only for the nobles and not for the common man, given to them by the king John in 1215 AD. Magna Carta was followed by 'Petition of Rights' (1627) and 'Bill of Rights' (1688). The American 'Bill of Rights' and the French Declaration of 'Rights of Man' (1789) were of a new consciousness, which acknowledged that rights of man were sacrosanct and hence they should be embodied in the constitutional law of modern states.

After the First World War, the world community for the first time released the need to establish some institutional mechanism to protect and preserve the rights of man. The establishment of the League of Nations was the first such attempt in this direction. However, it was only after UN Charter was signed in 1945 that any attempt was made to provide comprehensive protection to all individuals against all forms of injustice and human rights violation. In the Preamble of the UN Charter, the people of the United Nations expressed determination to reaffirm faith in the fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of human and in the equal rights of the men and women. The Charter makes repeated reference of human rights and fundamental freedoms.¹⁰

On 10 December 1948 the United Nations General Assembly adopted, the famous Universal Declaration of Human Rights, it can be said to be the first ever international effort to codify the fundamental human rights. It contains a preamble and 30 articles. It deals not only with civil and political but with social and economic rights also.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights was viewed as first step in the formulation of an "international Bill of Human Rights". In 1976, three decades after this comprehensive undertaking was launched by the United Nations, the 'International Bill of Human Rights' became a reality, with three significant instruments."

- The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural rights.
- The International Covenant on Civil and Political rights.
- The Optional Protocol to the latter Covenant.

The Declaration on Right to Development adopted by United Nations in 1986 is one of the most important basic human rights and constitutes the culminating point of the evolution of the concept of human rights. Many declarations, treaties and resolutions adopted by UN General Assembly deal with some aspects of human rights every year.¹²

There are a spectrum of independent organizations and nongovernmental organizations working for the promotion of human rights in various fields at a global level. A few among them are ILO (International Labour Organization), UNICEF (United Nations International Children's Emergency

Fund), WHO (World Health Organization), Amnesty International, International Red Cross Society etc.

Besides this, Human Rights Commission, Human Rights Commissioner, Centre for Human Rights is also working for the promotion of human rights.

Human Rights in Indian Context

Long before civilization dawned in Egypt and Greece, we have the Hindu jurisprudence of about 4000 BC. The Hindu jurists have the Hindu jurisprudence of about 4000 BC. "A king should enter the court room with all humility." "More Cruel than the man who lives the life of a murderer is the king who lets himself to oppress and act unjustly (towards his subjects)".

"For it is punishment alone that guards this world and the other, when it is evenly met by king to his son and his enemy, according to the offense." The Hindu jurists have elaborated the procedure for civil and criminal cases as well as investigations. Hindu jurists like Narada, Brhaspati and Katyayan have elaborated rules to the innocent and stressed that king should not shrink from punishing the guilty. The Indian mind, thousand of years before the dawn of Christian era, could perceive the existence of all living being in paramatman and visualized Paramatman in all creatures, thus leaving behind no room for hatred towards any one. The Vedic rishis always prayed for the well-being of everyone in society. These rishis were first to conceive the whole world as one family. In the above context, it was considered foremost duty of the state or king to protect the citizens or praja. The protection of citizens in those days was considered necessary from high officials, criminals, enemies of the state and from the kings and those who were close to him. One can very well realize how ancient is the concept of protecting rights of citizens against the avarice or greed of the king or the state.⁵ Rig Veda cites three civil rights-that is of Tana (Body), Skridhi (Dwelling place) and Jibhasi (Life). Mahabharata tells about the importance of the freedoms of the individual (civil liberties) in a state. Concept of Dharma-rights and duties of individuals, classes, communities and castes-has been delineated in our scriptures. Before second century BC. Indian states could boast of elected kings. Arthashashtra elaborates on civil and legal rights first formulated by Manu which also included economic rights.⁶

Another aspect which is important to be discussed in the Indian perspective is that our view toward rights is duty-centric and western views is right centric. It seems that root cause of all the problems which are creating hinderance in the realization of human rights is this right centric view. It sees men born with certain natural, inalienable, universal rights which can be 'ascribed to him just because he is a human being. On the other hand, our Indian i.e. duty-centric view emphasis that man is born with certain Rinas (debts) or obligations and it is his foremost Dharma (duty) that 'he discharges these obligations with almost care and perfection. Unless one does so, one is not considered worthy of being called a human being. The essence and meaning of human existence consists in fulfillment of certain obligations he is born with. To do so he may need certain privileges or facilities. He must be provided with these facilities. But he can possess these 'rightfully', only if he uses them for discharging his obligations. In this duty centric world view rights acquire a goal-oriented character. They are not cherished for their own sake. They are important, but their importance primarily lies in their instrumentality towards. specific goals.¹⁷

Development of Human Rights in India

The evolution of the concept of rights in our country, as a matter of fact, coincides with the growth of a struggle for national liberation and it has evolved precisely in the same manner in which our national movement has developed. The earlier phase of Indian National Movement Was led by upper middle class and the landlords; Therefore, it was only inevitable that the thrust was on civil and "political rights. With passage of time, national movement did not remain confined to the upper' classes only, it became a mass movement, the credit. for this goes to Mahatma Gandhi. He brought the rank and file of the Indian people into the folds of freedom struggle. The demand for the rights now became wider and people started demanding not only civil and political but socio-economic rights also. Mention should also be made of Gandhian approach to the concept of rights. Gandhiji was of the view that rights without duties are mere usurpation and therefore, each right should be followed by a duty.

The evolution of fundamental rights can be traced in two phases.

- a) Pre-Constituent Assembly Era, and
- b) Framing of Fundamental Rights by Constituent Assembly.

The first explicit demand for fundamental rights appeared in the Constitution of India Bill, 1895. Other documents 011' the rights of pre-assembly era were Annie Beasant's Common Wealth of India Bill 1925, Nehru Committee Report, 1928, Karachi Charter, 1931 and Sapru Committee Report 1945.

The Constituent Assembly came into existence in 1946. A Sub-Committee was appointed by the Advisory Committee to deal with the Fundamental Rights. The Advisory Committee accepted the following recommendations of Sub-Committee on Fundamental Rights;

- *For division of rights into justiciable and nonjusticiable rights;
- *Certain. rights guaranteed to all persons and certain other rights to the citizens only.
- All such rights being made uniformly applicable to the Union and the Units.

The Indian Constitution came into force on 26 January, 1950. The dream of Founding Fathers to make the India's Constitution a viable instrument for the Indian people's salvation and to secure all person basic human rights is implicit from the promise made in Preamble, Fundamental Rights and Directive Principles of the State Policy.

The Preamble of the Constitution is largely based on the Objective Resolution moved by Nehruji. It states in unequivocal term that the people of India solemnly resolved, "to secure all its citizens justicesocial, economic and political; liberty of thought, expression, belief, faith and worship; equality of status and opportunity, and to promote among them fraternity so as to secure the dignity of the individual and unity and integrity of the nation."

The philosophy underlying fundamental right is that constitutional limitation on the powers of the government are the only way of ensuring the survival of basic human freedom.

While enunciating rights for the Indian people, Founding Fathers kept in mind the requirements of the modern welfare state. it was clear in their mind that they had to prescribe rights for a country where the existence of a number of religious, linguistic and cultural minorities on one hand and the caste system on the other hand created problems which were peculiar to this country alone and if the purpose of a bill of rights was to usher in a new era wherein the human personality might find adequate avenues for self realization, it was essential that the fundamental rights as embodied in the

Constitution should provide satisfactory solution to these problems. The entire Chapter III of Constitution deals with the scheme of fundamental rights as guaranteed to every citizen.

The principles embodied in Chapter IV are directives to the various governments and government agencies (including village panchayats) to be followed as fundamental in the governance of the country. It shall be the duty of the state to apply these principles in making laws. Thus, they place an ideal before the legislators of India while they frame new legislation for the country's administration. They lay down a code of conduct for the administration of India while they discharge their responsibilities as agents of the sovereign power of the nation. In short, the Directive Principles enshrine the fundamentals for the realization of which the state in India stands. They guide the path, which lead the people Of India to achieve the noble ideals, which are embodied in the Preamble.

India took a lead in this behalf and enacted Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993. This Act besides other provisions provides for the creation Of a National Human Right Commission. The apex court Significantly held that it was fully empowered to look into the propriety of orders passed by such commissions and observed "the National Human Right Commission headed by a former chief justice Of India is a unique expert body in itself. The chairman of the commission in his capacity as a judge of Supreme Court or as a Chief Justice of India, and so also to other members, who have held high judicial offices as Chief justice of High Courts, have throughout their tenure. considered, expounded and enforced the fundamental rights and are. in their own way, expert in the fields. And the judiciary is also playing an important role in promoting and protecting human rights.

In the end, we can conclude that concept of human right is not merely western and modern but both the concept has evolved and developed in Indian and international perspective. The difference lies only in the approach towards the rights. Our approach is duty-centric and western view is right centric. It may be noted that this duty-based characterization of rights in no way diminishes their importance. Rather it seems to add new dimensions to it. The approach makes rights very specific, concrete and consequently more effective in the practical realm. They no more remain simply abstract principles capable of being differently interpreted or misinterpreted. They become concrete instruments of realizing the ultimate aims of human essence. Moreover, their derivation from moral obligation gives them significance of a 'Value' and in a way makes them elements of ideal realm.'¹⁹ In this perspective we can say that Indian approach to the concept of human rights has given a new vision to the whole world, to deal with theoretical and functional aspect of human rights. It has also given a practical solution to all the problems related to human rights as it focuses more on duties than on rights.

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